

Bayesian Inference and the Shape of the Primordial Universe

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ABSTRACT

Measurements of the curvature parameter Ω_K using different cosmological data sets have been shown to give conflicting results to a significance of at least 2.5σ (Handley 2021b). This work seeks to determine how one’s choice of prior affects the calculation of Ω_K , specifically the choice of a uniform curvature prior or a prior motivated by our understanding of inflation, resulting in a sharp peak at $\Omega_K = 0$. We compare the resulting Bayesian evidences for calculations using these two priors in an attempt to gauge the validity of our current inflationary models. We directly compare results that both do and do not include CMB lensing data, and results that use different sampling algorithms. We find that the choice of prior significantly affects the posterior distribution on Ω_K , as well as the evidence recovered. However, while a sharply peaked prior improves the model fit when using the lensing data set, the opposite is true for the data set with no lensing. We also find that using a sharply peaked prior still results in tails to negative values in the Ω_K posteriors. Finally, we show that widening and narrowing the peaked prior does not result in significant changes in the Bayesian evidence. The fact that the two data sets considered are optimally fit by two different models leads us to the conclusion that a curvature tension is present, and cannot be explained away by choice of prior.

Key words: cosmology: cosmological parameters — cosmology: inflation — cosmology: early Universe

1 INTRODUCTION

In our modern era of precision cosmology, potential cracks are beginning to show in our theory of the universe, with the Hubble Tension holding strong and arguably worsening over the past few years (Riess et al. 2022). It might be easier to dismiss this discrepancy if other tensions were not also observed in other fundamental parameters such as S_8 , related to the amplitude of matter fluctuations, and Ω_K , the curvature parameter of our universe and subject of this work.

The “curvature tension” in this parameter is revealed when the Λ CDM model is fit to different cosmological data sets (Handley 2021b), whereby different data sets give differing values of Ω_K . The Λ CDM model represents our current best understanding of the evolution and the shape of the universe, supported by precise observations from the Planck satellite of the cosmic microwave background (CMB). These measurements allow us to extract values for the six fundamental parameters that govern the Λ CDM model and Ω_K by comparing the predictions these models make to the statistical properties of the CMB or other cosmological phenomena.

The value of Ω_K has profound implications for our understanding of the universe. A key element in the story of the Λ CDM model is inflation, and while the predictions of inflation have been experimentally verified to 8σ (Planck Collaboration 2020b), the exact cause of inflation remains a mystery. However, we are able to predict that inflation should have a flattening effect on the universe, pushing Ω_K towards zero

(Guth 1981; Efstathiou & Gratton 2021). This strong theoretical prediction, along with the added computational ease of neglecting curvature, has led to spatial flatness being a common assumption in the literature (Glanville et al. 2022).

An observation of a non-zero value of Ω_K would place constraints on what caused inflation and how it occurred (Hergt et al. 2022). In addition, Ω_K being non-zero would render the universe to a finite size, meaning perturbation modes would be quantized rather than continuous (Bartlett et al. 2022; Prathaban & Handley 2022). Finally, terms in the Boltzmann equations — which describe how different species of perturbation (photons, baryons, dark matter, etc.) evolve with time — are curvature dependent, meaning that a non-flat universe will have a different cosmological history than a purely flat one (Hergt et al. 2022).

This work seeks to explore the effect that the choice of prior has on one’s measurement of Ω_K . The choice of whether to use a “curvature agnostic” (i.e. uniform) prior or one that reflects our understanding of inflation by being strongly peaked at $\Omega_K = 0$ has been discussed in the literature (Efstathiou & Gratton 2020) but the quality of their fits has not been directly compared. By comparing the resulting fit quality of the two priors considered, we aim to determine if the our current understanding of inflation is supported by the data, or if a model making no assumptions about inflation is a better representation of reality. This goal of comparing priors motivates our use of `Polychord`, a dynamic nested sampling

algorithm, as algorithms of this type more fully explore the prior space than MCMC algorithms (Speagle 2020).

Whether the tension is a statistical coincidence, a sign of systematic errors in the data, or a hint at new physics, resolving it will give even greater confidence in the Λ CDM model or lead us toward a new understanding of the universe. This work intends to help find this resolution using state-of-the-art data, code, and statistical methods to compare different priors on Ω_K and their resulting posteriors. We will also compare the Bayesian evidences to determine which prior offers the best fit to different data sets in an attempt to explain or further understand the curvature tension. This report is organised as follows. In §2 we explore the works that discover and seek to explain the curvature tension. In §3 we give an overview of the background theory needed to address the curvature tension, and in §4 we discuss the statistical and computational methods used in our calculations. In §5 we discuss the data used, and in §6 we pay special attention to how the prior enters our code. We give results, a discussion, and conclude in §7, §8, and §9. The laboratory notebook for this project can be found at this [link](#). Except where specific reference is made to the work of others, this work is original and has not been already submitted either wholly or in part to satisfy any degree requirement at this or any other university.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The Planck 2018 CMB data release favors a universe that is statistically significantly closed, $\Omega_K = -0.045 \pm 0.015$ (Planck Collaboration 2020a,b). Other data sets such as Planck 2018 CMB lensing (Planck Collaboration 2020c) or Baryon Acoustic Oscillations (BAO) (Alam 2017; Beutler et al. 2011; Ross et al. 2015) favor a flat universe with $\Omega_K = 0$. This discrepancy is partly caused by disagreements between theory and observation about the amount of lensing in the universe; we observe an amount of lensing that is 2σ more than predicted. Closed cosmological models offer an explanation for this phenomenon through their increased value of Ω_m which would generate more lensing (Glanville et al. 2022). However, it is possible that this effect is coincidence (Efstathiou & Gratton 2021; Planck Collaboration 2016, 2020b), and more generally, a closed cosmology would require an inflationary period with fewer e-foldings (the number of times the universe grows by a factor of e during inflation), in conflict with Planck data (Glanville et al. 2022). Joint fits using multiple sources of data tend to prefer flatness as well, though issues have been raised concerning how viable it is to combine multiple data sources in this way (Glanville et al. 2022; Handley 2021b).

Another factor that could be driving conflict between data sets is the use of fiducial cosmologies. In order to use certain data sets, such as BAO, to measure cosmological parameters, one needs to assume a model of the universe to make the calculation. Hence, if one uses a Flat Λ CDM model, but the universe is in fact slightly closed, this could bias results. Glanville et al. (2022) test this hypothesis by repeatedly fitting Ω_K with different fiducial cosmologies, and find that this biasing effect does exist, but is smaller than the statistical noise present. Nevertheless, subtle effects such as this one could be the root cause of the tension.

3 BACKGROUND AND THEORY

3.1 Λ CDM

The current leading general model of cosmology is the Λ CDM model (Scott 2018). Λ represents the inclusion of the cosmological constant, i.e. dark energy, in this model. CDM stands for cold dark matter, cold meaning that dark matter particles were non-relativistic at the time when contributions to the expansion of the universe from radiation and matter components were equal. This model is governed by six parameters. Ω_b and Ω_c are the densities of baryonic matter and cold dark matter respectively, given as fractions of the critical density. Another parameter is H_0 , the current rate of expansion of the universe. τ is the reionization optical depth, a number quantifying how much of the light from the epoch of reionization is reaching us today, as opposed to being absorbed or deflected by intermittent matter. n_s is the scalar spectral index, which represents how the amplitudes of density fluctuations vary with their scale. In particular, if one models the power spectrum of density perturbations as a simple power law, the scalar spectral index appears in the exponent:

$$P(k) \propto k^{n_s-1}, \quad (1)$$

where k is the wavelength of the perturbation mode. Therefore, $n_s = 1$ corresponds to the case where perturbations are the same amplitude at all wavelengths (Madore 1997). The final parameter is Δ_R^2 , the amplitude of curvature fluctuations in the universe.

For reasons mentioned in the introduction, this model assumes the universe is perfectly flat. The fits we will perform with *Cobaya* in this project will include curvature (Ω_K) as a free parameter, typically called the K Λ CDM model.

3.2 The Curvature Parameter

The solutions to the Friedmann equations allow for the possibility that the universe could be closed, open, or flat, which corresponds to the curvature parameter, Ω_K , taking on a negative, positive, or zero value. These geometries can be understood in their effects on object paths. Two photons fired in parallel lines will stay an equal distance apart for all time in a flat universe, as one would expect. However, in a closed universe parallel lines eventually intersect, and in an open universe they would diverge.

Measurements of the curvature parameter can be extracted from cosmological data sets. For the CMB, this involves decomposing the two-dimensional map of the temperature or polarisation into spherical harmonics and re-expressing this as a one-dimensional power spectrum. Assuming Gaussian, adiabatic, and scale invariant primordial quantum fluctuations, one can predict the statistical properties of the power spectrum of the CMB we observe (Freedman 2000). Thus, predictions of the six Λ CDM parameters and Ω_K can be made by fitting the cosmological models to the observed power spectrum.

3.3 Inflation

By the 1980s, astrophysicists knew the universe was approximately flat. However, we know that the condition of flatness is highly unstable (Guth 1981), and any slight deviation from

$\Omega_K = 0$ will cause the curvature to quickly change away from flat. In order to observe a flat universe now, the universe’s parameters would have to be incredibly finely tuned (to within a factor of 10^{-55}) so as to balance the universe at $\Omega_K = 0$ despite the instability. This cosmic coincidence explanation is extremely unlikely and quite unsatisfying.

However, an exponential expansion of the universe would force the curvature parameter to be close to zero without relying on hand-waving appeals to fine-tuned universal constants. This success, along with solutions to other cosmological problems, has made inflation a staple of modern models of the early universe. However, we have yet to have a satisfactory explanation of what actually causes this inflation. The phenomenon could be well explained by a scalar “inflaton” field permeating the universe (Lidsey et al. 1997), but any attempts to assign a real scalar field such as the Higgs field this role has led to mixed results (Atkins & Calmet 2011). Further study is necessary to understand the driving force behind inflation, which is the goal of this project. A concrete measurement of a value of Ω_K that is statistically distinct from zero would place constraints on what models of inflation are potentially valid and could lead to insights on its cause or duration (Herget et al. 2022; Efstathiou & Gratton 2020), while a measurement statistically consistent with zero would support our current understanding of inflation.

4 METHODS

4.1 Bayesian Statistics

This project will use Bayesian statistics to derive possible values of the curvature parameter. Bayesian statistics is a useful result of probability theory that allows us to predict the likelihood of certain results (say, a certain parameter) based on both data we have and on our prior knowledge about the system in question. Bayesian statistics is built fundamentally on Bayes’ theorem:

$$P(\theta|D) = \frac{P(D|\theta)P(\theta)}{P(D)} \quad (2)$$

In this equation, D is the data we are trying to model, and θ is the collection of parameters in that model. P means “the probability of” and the vertical bar $x|y$ is shorthand for “ x given y ”. Therefore, $P(\theta|D)$ is the likelihood of our model parameters taking certain values θ for given data D ; this quantity is called the posterior and will allow us to extract a final result and error bars. $P(D|\theta)$ is called the likelihood, which represents how unlikely or likely it is that our data could be measured if our model (θ) is correct. $P(\theta)$ is called the prior and is the heart of what sets Bayesian statistics apart from other methods. The prior is the likelihood of certain model parameters given no data, in essence, it represents our pre-conceived notions about what θ should be. The inclusion of a prior can be seen as a strength or a weakness of Bayes’ Theorem, as the prior is inherently subjective. However, it can be incredibly useful when incorporating previous results or predictions of related theories. The denominator, $P(D)$ is called the evidence and can be calculated from the prior and likelihood:

$$P(D) = \int P(D|\theta)P(\theta)d\theta \quad (3)$$

Beyond just assessing the likelihood of different parameters, Bayesian statistics allows us to draw conclusions on which model is a better description of the data. We want to calculate and compare values of $P(M|D)$, the likelihood of the model, M , given the data. You may notice that this is of the exact same form as the left-hand side of Equation 2, and therefore

$$P(M|D) = \frac{P(D|M)P(M)}{P(D)}. \quad (4)$$

$P(D|M)$ is calculable as the evidence from our parameter-level application of Bayes’ theorem, and the prior is typically taken as uniform. The respective values and their ratio, called the Bayes Factor, will allow us to place “betting odds” on which model is more likely to represent reality (Trotta 2008; Handley 2021a).

4.2 Markov Chain Monte Carlo

Unfortunately, using real-world data makes these calculations exceedingly difficult to solve by hand. Therefore, we tend to rely on Markov-Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling. In general, the numerator of equation 2 will be easy to calculate, but the denominator will not be. How to sample from $P(\theta|D)$ without knowing $P(D)$ is known as the Sampling Problem and can be solved through the use of MCMC algorithms (Haugh 2017). We do this by sampling from the distribution until we have a good approximation. To generate these samples, we need an algorithm that takes an arbitrary chain of numbers and approaches our desired distribution, such as the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm or the Gibbs sampler. Numerically integrating over the samples will then give us an approximate result. Note that, by virtue of the law of large numbers, this should approach the true value as the number of samples grows large (Reinert 2005).

4.3 Nested Sampling and Polychord

This work also makes use of Polychord (Handley et al. 2015), a nested sampling (Skilling 2006) algorithm specifically designed for exploring the high dimensionality parameter spaces in cosmology.

The problem that nested sampling addresses is the same as that of MCMC: sampling from some distribution is difficult. A colloquial way to understand the difference between these two methods is that MCMC is trying to solve a hard problem once (generating chains that converge onto the desired distribution) while nested sampling tries to simplify the issue at hand and solve that problem repeatedly. It does this by slicing the likelihood, sampling the slices, and recombining these slices at the end of the algorithm (Speagle 2021).

The nested sampling method is useful due to its ability to calculate both the evidence and the posterior, whereas MCMC typically can only compute one, and avoids the burn-in phase that MCMC necessitates. However, nested sampling does require one to know or calculate an appropriate prior transform, and estimating the evidence does require sampling the entirety of the distribution, rather than just regions of interest, and hence increases computation time (Speagle 2020).

One can further improve the performance of nested sampling through dynamic nested sampling methods. These algorithms use the same basic principles but allow for the number

Figure 1. One and two dimensional posteriors for the six Λ CDM parameters, generated using Cobaya.

of sampling points, called live points, to vary throughout the calculation. By allocating samples more efficiently, i.e. using more live points in regions we determine to be more important, dynamic nested sampling can both reduce calculation time and improve the accuracy of the results (Higson et al. 2019). A more in-depth look at both sampling algorithms used is given in Appendix C.

We utilize these sampling methods and access cosmological likelihoods through Cobaya (COde for BAYesian Analysis) (Torrado & Lewis 2019; Torrado & Lewis 2021). This code allows us to select the cosmological likelihoods and Boltzmann solvers we wish to use, while also including custom priors. We use it to implement both MCMC and Polychord samplers to calculate Ω_K . We show an example of a typical Cobaya output for a flat universe using Polychord in Figure 1.

5 DATA

This work relies on several data sets and their likelihoods in order to extract measurements of Ω_K . We use gravitational lensing, polarization, and temperature anisotropy maps of the CMB from the Planck 2018 data release (Planck Collaboration 2020a,b,c, 2016). We specifically take advantage of their temperature map at low multipole values, abbreviated TT, the polarization at low multipole, abbreviated EE, and

a combined temperature and polarization map, abbreviated TTTEEE.

We also utilize the CAMB cosmological code (Lewis et al. 2000; Howlett et al. 2012) which calculates CMB, lensing, galaxy count, dark-age 21cm power spectra, and matter power spectra while also computing transfer functions, which describe how these power spectra evolve with time as a function of wavelength.

6 PRIORS

Up unto this point, this report has been literature review, background, and theory. The remainder of this thesis is purely my own work.

As so much of this project depends on measuring the effects of different priors, we take a moment to consider their implementation in more depth here. As noted in Efstathiou & Gratton (2020), one needs to be careful when implementing a prior, as assuming an overly simplistic model can return a useless result for the evidence (Efstathiou 2008). A well-motivated prior should be backed by some theoretical prediction about the system you are considering. Of course, when the system is not fully understood, there can be multiple disagreeing theories about the system in question, and hence you can have multiple possible priors for your Bayesian analysis. In this case, we can consider the prior as an integral

Figure 2. The shape of the prior from [Efstathiou & Gratton \(2020\)](#) given as equation 5 with varying values for the α parameter.

part of our overall model, and hence compare the priors by using standard Bayesian model comparison methods. In this way, the model with the better fit can be said to be a more accurate reflection of the system, and hence the theory that gave rise to the winning prior is more likely to be correct. This is the method we will use to compare different pictures of the early universe, one where inflation is taken for granted and curvature should be forced to be near flat, and one that treats all potential curvatures equally.

The priors we will compare in this work are a “curvature agnostic” uniform prior, and the sharply peaked prior representing the predictions of inflation given as equation 4 in [Efstathiou & Gratton \(2020\)](#), originally derived in [Freivogel et al. \(2006\)](#):

$$p(\Omega_K)d\Omega_K = \frac{(\alpha - 1)}{4} \frac{N_*^{(\alpha-1)}}{(N_* - \frac{1}{2} \ln|\Omega_K|)^\alpha} \frac{d\Omega_K}{\Omega_K}. \quad (5)$$

In this equation, N_* is the minimum number of e-foldings that will solve the flatness problem, which is about 60. α is the slope of the power law of the prior on N , the actual number of e-foldings, assuming that $N > N_*$:

$$p(N)dN \propto N^{-\alpha}dN, \quad N > N_* \quad (6)$$

The shape of the Ω_K prior is shown for several α values in Figure 2.

There are several ways to include a prior in a **Cobaya** run. Firstly, one can include the prior by passing the function defining the percent point function, cumulative distribution function, et cetera of the prior directly into the .yaml file. In the **Cobaya** documentation this is referred to as an “external prior”, and in taking this more official route the prior will undergo the unit hypercube transformation characteristic of nested sampling, if nested sampling is being used. Secondly, one can enter the code that defines the prior directly into

MCMC	Lensing	No Lensing
Efstathiou Prior	$0.00^{+0.00}_{-0.001}$	$0.00^{+0.017}_{-0.030}$
Uniform Prior	$-0.010^{+0.006}_{-0.006}$	$-0.042^{+0.017}_{-0.017}$

Table 1. Calculated values of Ω_K using an MCMC sampler.

the code of **Cobaya**, referred to affectionately as “monkey-patching”. This slightly more brute-force method adds the prior directly into the log-likelihood calculations as an additional density term. We ultimately choose this second route, as the external prior method has a tendency to give a timeout error.

7 RESULTS

In order to fully explore the possibilities that could be behind the curvature tension, we decide to perform a **Cobaya** run with each possible combination in each of our three variables: uniform vs. Efstathiou prior, MCMC vs. **Polychord**, and lensing vs. no lensing, leading to a total of eight combinations. We also run a zero curvature Λ CDM model for comparison to the curved models. This is shown in Figure 1 to illustrate the typical **Cobaya** output.

7.1 Comparing the Uniform and Efstathiou Priors

The recovered posteriors on Ω_K using MCMC are shown in Figure 3. The calculated values of Ω_K are given in Table 1.

Including lensing forces both prior cases towards $\Omega_K = 0$, which has also been seen in previous analyses ([Handley 2021b](#)), and using the Efstathiou prior also forces the distribution towards $\Omega_K = 0$ as is to be expected.

The results for the same four cases but using **Polychord** are shown in Table 2. As the posterior shapes are quite similar to the MCMC case, we include the figure showing them in the appendix, Figure A1. The uniform prior results are remarkably similar in both the MCMC and **Polychord** cases, covering almost the exact same range of values. We find similar overall trends to the MCMC case, where including lensing and switching to the Efstathiou prior pushes the distributions towards zero. In general, the MCMC and **Polychord** results agree quite well, though they disagree slightly on the width of the distributions in the Efstathiou prior case. This is likely due to **Polychord** more completely exploring the tails of the prior, which will be more important for the Efstathiou prior due to its shape.

Our results using a uniform prior and excluding or including lensing are consistent with [Planck Collaboration \(2020a,b\)](#) and [Handley \(2021b\)](#) respectively; this is true for both the MCMC and **Polychord** results. No analogues for the Efstathiou prior results exist in the literature to the best of our knowledge.

Arguably more important than the exact value of Ω_K for our analysis are the associated evidences for each fit. As mentioned in section 4.3, we only have these values for **Polychord** calculations, as only nested sampling gives both the evidence and the posterior. The values of the logarithm of the evidence, $\log(Z)$ are recorded in Table 3. Note that the evidences in the lensing versus no lensing case change in opposing directions

Figure 3. Calculated posteriors of Ω_K using an MCMC sampler. The upper plot utilizes Planck CMB lensing data, while the bottom does not. In each plot, the orange line shows the posterior when a sharply peaked Efstathiou prior is used, while the blue line shows the posterior in the uniform prior case.

Polychord	Lensing	No Lensing
Efstathiou Prior	$(0.0^{+0.5}_{-0.0}) \times 10^{-23}$	$0.00^{+0.00}_{-0.02}$
Uniform Prior	$-0.010^{+0.006}_{-0.007}$	$-0.042^{+0.016}_{-0.019}$

Table 2. Calculated values of Ω_K using Polychord.

log(Z) values for Polychord	Lensing	No Lensing
Flat Λ CDM	-1445.6 ± 0.2	-1441.3 ± 0.2
Efstathiou Prior	-1445.8 ± 0.2	-1440.9 ± 0.2
Uniform Prior	-1448.2 ± 0.2	-1439.0 ± 0.2

Table 3. The values of the logarithm of the evidence for the four main Polychord runs considered in this work.

when switching to the Efstathiou prior, which will be further analysed in §8.

Another interesting way of looking at these results is to convert them from probability density distributions to probability mass functions, and then to rescale this distribution into σ significance values. We do this as follows. We define the probability mass function (PMF) as the integral over a histogram over the region where the height of the histogram is below a certain threshold. Sliding this threshold from the minimum histogram height to the maximum and recording the probability mass below each threshold will give us a curve that by definition increases monotonically from zero to one. This is the probability mass function; an example of a PMF

and an illustration of how it is constructed is given in Figure 4.

We can convert probability mass into σ using the standard relation $\sigma = \sqrt{2} \times \text{erfinv}(1 - p)$, where erfinv is the inverse error function and p is the probability mass. We then remap our starting histogram using this function. The height in each bin of the histogram corresponds to an x value in the PMF, we rescale the histogram to the matching y value. Results for this analysis are shown in Figure 5.

These plots show that in all cases the posteriors generated using the Efstathiou and uniform prior begin to agree at about the 2σ level. This demonstrates that the peak at $\Omega_K = 0$ whenever the Efstathiou prior is used is not as overpowering to the rest of the data as it might appear at first glance. While it is tall, a notable amount of the probability mass escapes the peak and forms a distribution similar in shape to the uniform prior case. Assuming the universe was flat, we would expect to see the samples stay at $\Omega_K = 0$ after having been forced there by the prior, but they actually escape this incredibly sharp peak. Using the Efstathiou prior makes the result statistically consistent with zero, but this does not answer the question of why the posterior still has a tail to negative values in all cases.

The evidences changing in opposing directions and the shape of the significance distributions seen in Figure 5 demonstrate that the Efstathiou prior is not unarguably superior to a uniform prior. Because of this, we seek to determine if modifying the Efstathiou prior can result in a better fit.

Figure 4. A visual representation of how Figure 5 was created. The shaded region below where histogram bars are below the dotted line are integrated over, and as the dotted line is scrolled up we generate the probability mass function in the bottom figure by recording the value of the integral at every step.

7.2 Modifying the Efstathiou Prior

According to Efstathiou & Gratton (2020), the parameter α in the Efstathiou prior is only restricted to be greater than 1. We took $\alpha = 2$ arbitrarily, but this is not the only value one could take. We thus decide to explore the effect different values of α have on the recovered posteriors and evidences. We perform three additional runs using Polychord and lensing, setting $\alpha = 1.1, 3,$ and 5 . The changing shape of the prior with these values is shown in Figure 2. The results for the posteriors on Ω_K are unsurprising: as α increases, more of the probability mass is distributed away from the peak and into the tails of the prior, and we observe a similar phenomenon in the results, see Figure 6. We quantify this in Table 4 by giving the fraction of samples contained within the $\Omega_K = 0$ peak, which we define as $|\Omega_K| < 10^{-4}$.

These results are meaningless, however, if the evidence shows that one value of α is strongly preferred over the others. Comparing the evidences of these runs gives the data shown in Table 4 and visualised in Figure 7. The data show no preferred value of α ; this will be discussed in the following section.

8 DISCUSSION

This project’s main goal was to determine the effect changing the prior had on the resulting evidences. We observe that changing the prior results in a statistically significant change in the evidence, see Table 3. This is not a foregone conclusion, earlier runs using lower number of live points (not displayed) found that changing the prior gave evidences that were statistically consistent with each other. Increasing the live points by a factor of ten, to one thousand in total, gives the results in this work. In the lensing case, the Efstathiou prior gives a better fit to the data, as the logarithm of the evidence increases by 2.4 (12σ) as compared to the uniform prior. This is unsurprising if we do live in a flat universe, as we have essentially forced the sampling algorithm to the “right” answer with the Efstathiou prior, giving a better fit. However, this does not match the result we see in the no lensing case; using the Efstathiou prior causes the logarithm of the evidence to decrease by 1.9 (9.5σ), an almost exactly opposite result.

This result demonstrates that the choice of prior is not the solution to the curvature tension problem. If we had seen one of the two priors improve the results for both data sets, we could claim that that represented a preference in the data for that model. However, the differing ratios of Bayesian evidences show that the Efstathiou prior model is a better fit to data including lensing, while an agnostic curvature prior is a better fit to data without lensing. Based on this analysis, the disagreement between the lensing and no lensing data sets is robust and fundamental to the existence of a curvature tension.

Furthermore, if the universe is flat, the shape of the distributions seen in Figure 5 undermine the ability of the Efstathiou prior to resolve the curvature tension. The peak in the distributions at $\Omega_K = 0$ is only distinct to about 2σ , which is not as significant as one would expect when the prior essentially forces $\Omega_K = 0$. The fact that some points leave the peak and venture to negative values indicates that the Efstathiou prior may not be the optimal prior for this system, by the same logic as above. This inspired us to seek how modifications to the Efstathiou prior would change these results.

To do this, we varied the α parameter. We found that there was no statistically significant preference for any of the values of α considered using the lensing data set; the maximum distance from the mean value of the four points considered being 2.2σ . A subtle upward trend is observed, but fitting a line to it determines that it is only statistically distinct from flat to the 1.3σ level. We interpret this result as further confirmation that the Efstathiou prior will not resolve the curvature tension. This is because, if the universe is truly flat, we would expect that the prior closest to a Dirac delta function centred at zero should be the best fit and the wider priors should give increasingly poor fits. In this scenario Figure 7 would show a decreasing trend, when in fact it shows a flat or possibly increasing line. This may demonstrate that a prior as sharp as the one considered in this work is not the optimal fit to the data, but another prior centred at zero could be. A more robust conclusion on the validity of this prior would require more values of α to be tested, as we discuss in §9.

Figure 5. Calculated posteriors of Ω_K using MCMC sampling and Polychord, similar to Figure 3, but the y axis has been rescaled to be in terms of σ of significance. Both priors are considered, as well as both the lensing and no lensing data sets.

9 CONCLUSION

In this work, we explored how the choice of prior affects the recovery of the curvature parameter Ω_K in an attempt to address the curvature tension in the literature, and to determine what these results could tell us about the theory of inflation.

Our results using a uniform prior agreed with results in

the literature, confirming our algorithms were working as intended. Once we included the Efstathiou prior, our results found that not only does using different priors significantly affect the value of Ω_K recovered, the quality of fit of the models used to make these calculations is strongly prior-dependent, causing greater than 9σ shifts in calculated evidence. How-

	$\alpha = 1.1$	$\alpha = 2$	$\alpha = 3$	$\alpha = 5$
$\log(Z)$	-1446.0 ± 0.2	-1445.8 ± 0.2	-1446.2 ± 0.2	-1445.4 ± 0.2
Fraction of samples with $ \Omega_K < 10^{-4}$	0.993	0.933	0.874	0.778

Table 4. Recovered values for the logarithm of the evidence, $\log(Z)$ as well as the fraction of samples contained within the peak at $\Omega_K = 0$, with cutoffs defined as $\pm 10^{-4}$. These results use the lensing data set.

Figure 6. Shown above are the posteriors of Ω_K calculated using Polychord, where we have chosen four different values for the parameter α in the sharply peaked Efstathiou prior, see Figure 2. For larger α values, the Ω_K posterior obtains a wider distribution around zero, and the median Ω_K value shifts slightly further from zero.

Figure 7. The recovered logarithm of evidence values for the different values of α considered is shown above. The 1σ confidence region for the uniform prior is shown as dotted lines for reference.

ever, the effect that the prior has on the evidence is nearly exactly opposite for the two data sets considered, one using Planck lensing and the other not.

This work was motivated by the suggestion of Efstathiou & Gratton (2020), who argue that the choice of a prior cannot be made half-heartedly. Evidently they are correct in this regard, but the results we find when changing priors show that choosing a well-motivated prior like the one we used

in this work is not enough to resolve the curvature tension. Different data sets seem to prefer different priors for models of the early universe, and the samples that escape the peak at $\Omega_K = 0$ forced by the Efstathiou prior seem to approximate the results found with the uniform prior. Evidently, whatever is causing the difference between the lensing and non-lensing data sets is intrinsic to the data, and cannot be resolved by choice of prior.

Of course, the fact that the problem is not solved could be due to the specific prior we chose. To address this, we varied the α parameter in the Efstathiou prior, and found that it did not result in a statistically significant change in Bayesian evidence. However, it could be that the four values of α simply do not change the prior enough to be noticeable compared to intrinsic noise in the data, resulting in similar evidences. We therefore suggest multiple possible extensions to this work. Firstly, we recommend further exploring the parameter space that controls the Efstathiou prior. α can only extend up to about $2N$ before the nature of the prior significantly changes, so there is a finite region to explore.

A new conclusion about the prior’s contribution to the curvature tension could be drawn from how evidence evolves with α . If evidence increases with α up to some maximum (it cannot increase monotonically, higher values of α approach a uniform distribution which we saw to have a lesser evidence value) this version of the Efstathiou prior would be the best fit to the data. Comparing the evidences for the lensing and no lensing cases here would have the best chance of improving evidences for both data sets and resolving the curvature tension.

If one repeated this analysis for the no lensing case and found a value for α where the Efstathiou prior increases evidence rather than decreases it, this could be a possible resolution to the curvature tension. This would likely occur at $\alpha > 2$, as larger α values are more similar to the uniform prior, which has higher evidence in the no lensing case. However, if one took this to mean that the universe is flat, they would still have to reconcile why they had to go to larger α values, which result in priors closer to uniform and give wider Ω_K posteriors, see Table 4.

Another possible extension is to vary N . An even more advanced analysis might allow N to be completely free in the fitting process, since α defines a probability distribution for N . Finally, one could explore different priors that are predicted by other models of inflation. Comparing evidences found with those priors to these results here could allow us to further constrain what models of inflation are viable.

This analysis found that the choice of prior can not reconcile the difference between these two data sets, demonstrating the tension in the curvature parameter is not easily dismissable. Regardless of whether the universe is closed or flat, the

disagreement between these data sets needs to be understood if they are to be useful for cosmology.

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APPENDIX A: POLYCHORD Ω_K POSTERIORS

Here we include an additional figure, which shows the posteriors of Ω_K calculated using `Polychord`, which we did not include above as it is largely similar to the MCMC case. See Figure A1.

APPENDIX B: PYTHON CODE FOR IMPLEMENTING PRIORS

In an attempt to circumvent future delays for projects similar to this one, below I include the code used to implement the sharply peaked Efstathiou prior:

```
class EfstPrior(stats.rv_continuous):
    def pdf(self, x, **kwd):
        a = globalalpha
        N = globalN
        term1 = (a - 1)/4
        num = N**(a-1)
        denom = \
            (N - (0.5 * \
                np.log(np.abs(x))))**a
        return np.abs(\
            (term1 * num)/(denom*x))
    def logpdf(self, x, **kwd):
        return np.log(self.pdf(x, **kwd))
    def cdf(self, x):
        a = globalalpha
        N = globalN
        return np.sign(x) * \
            -(2**(a-2))*N**(a-1)\
                * (-1)/(2*N - np.log(\
                    np.abs(x)))*(a-1)\
                + 0.5
    def ppf(self, x, **kwd):
        a = globalalpha
        N = globalN
        return np.exp(2*N-(2**(2-a)\
            *(np.abs(x-0.5))*N**(1-a))\
            *(1/(1-a)))* np.sign(x-0.5)
stats.efsprior = EfstPrior(name='efsprior')
```

This code can be utilized by simply copy-and-pasting it into the `tools.py` file in `Cobaya`. Then one can use it by setting “dist” under “prior” in your `.yaml` file to be ‘efsprior’. The idea to make this prior into an object recognized by `scipy`, i.e. the last line of code above, was Lukas Hergt’s, so again many thanks are in order.

To give this function access to differing values of α I defined global variables for both α and N . There are almost certainly cleaner ways to do this, but every other route gave errors, so I resort to this method. In the `tools.py` file I replace the following line:

```
pdf_dist = getattr(import_module\
    ("scipy.stats", dist), dist)
```

with:

```
if param == 'omk':
    try:
        global globalalpha
        global globalN
        globalalpha = info2['loc']
        globalN = info2['scale']
        print(globalalpha, globalN)
    except:
        pass
```

```
pdf_dist = getattr(import_module\
    ("scipy.stats", dist), dist)
```

In the above code, I have reused the built-in `Cobaya` keywords ‘loc’ and ‘scale’ to act as inputs for α and N . To do so, simply set `loc` and `scale` to be 2 and 60, or whatever values, in your `.yaml` file. Altogether it might look like this:

```
omk:
    prior:
        dist: 'efsprior'
        loc: 2
        scale: 60
        latex: \Omega_k
```

While I am unsure if anyone will perform further research using this exact prior, I hope this is useful if one needs to include priors in this non-traditional method in future projects by simply modifying the above code to whatever prior you are using.

APPENDIX C: ALGORITHMS USED

Here we elaborate on the algorithms that were used in this work, as mentioned in §4.

C1 MCMC

Consider some random variable X with a distribution π , and some function $h(x)$. If we want to calculate an expectation value:

$$E_{\pi}[h(X)] = \int h(x)\pi(x)dx, \quad (C1)$$

it will likely be quite difficult to do analytically. However, if we can sample π , creating samples $x^i \sim \pi$ we can estimate

Figure A1. Calculated posteriors of Ω_K using `Polychord`. The upper plot utilizes Planck CMB lensing data, while the bottom does not. In each plot, the orange line shows the posterior when a sharply peaked Efstathiou prior is used, while the blue line shows the posterior in the uniform prior case.

this integral via:

$$E_\pi[h(X)] \approx \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n h(x^i). \quad (\text{C2})$$

(Reinert 2005) This means that rather than integrating over the posterior, which may be difficult, we can calculate this simple sum.

C2 Nested Sampling

Say we are trying to evaluate the typically difficult to compute evidence integral (equation 3). One way of approaching this problem is by slicing our many-dimensional space up using iso-likelihood contours. This is similar to how one might choose to integrate over spherical shells when trying to calculate the volume of a sphere. Each of these contours will have some associated probability, and an associated volume element again, like in a spherical shell integral (Speagle 2020). Because of this analogy, we call the integral over the prior in the regime where the likelihood is greater than the likelihood contour the prior volume:

$$X(\lambda) \equiv \int_{\mathcal{L}(\Theta) > \lambda} \pi(\Theta) d\Theta \quad (\text{C3})$$

where \mathcal{L} is our likelihood, λ is the value of the likelihood at the contour, π is our prior, and Θ represents the parameters of our model. With this definition, we can reframe our evidence integral as an integral over prior volume:

$$\mathcal{Z} = \int_{\Omega_\Theta} \mathcal{L}(\Theta) \pi(\Theta) d\Theta = \int_0^1 \mathcal{L}(X) dX \quad (\text{C4})$$

This integral is from 0 to 1 as the volume elements are normalized to the size of the prior by definition, see equation C3. However, calculating X and dX is still difficult, so we will approximate them via sampling.

To begin sampling, the algorithm generates some number of “live points” sampled from the prior. At each iteration, the live point with the lowest likelihood is added to a list of dead points, and a new live point is drawn with the constraint that its likelihood must be greater than the minimum likelihood just calculated. The leftover dead points allow us to calculate the change in X at each iteration (Speagle 2020). This process continues until some stopping criterion is reached, generally when an estimate of the remaining evidence we have not integrated over becomes lower than some desired threshold. At this point, we repeat the process of converting live points into dead points but no longer replace them, until we have converted all of the live points into dead points. Now, our sample of dead points, Θ_k , can be used to calculate the evidence integral through a simple numerical integration:

$$\hat{\mathcal{Z}} = \sum_{i=1}^{N+K} \frac{1}{2} [\mathcal{L}(\Theta_{i-1}) + \mathcal{L}(\Theta_i)] \times [\hat{X}_{i-1} - \hat{X}_i] \quad (\text{C5})$$

where N is the number of iterations before stopping, and K is the number of live points used. An added advantage of nested sampling is that we also determine the posterior simultaneously with no extra effort. It can be calculated from the same set of dead points. By defining the importance weight as the terms in the sum above:

$$\hat{p}_i \equiv \frac{1}{2} [\mathcal{L}(\Theta_{i-1}) + \mathcal{L}(\Theta_i)] \times [\hat{X}_{i-1} - \hat{X}_i] \quad (\text{C6})$$

the posterior is estimated as:

$$\hat{p}(\Theta) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N+K} \hat{p}(\Theta_i) \delta(\Theta_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^{N+K} \hat{p}(\Theta_i)} = \hat{Z}^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^{N+K} \hat{p}(\Theta_i) \delta(\Theta_i) \quad (\text{C7})$$

with δ being the Dirac delta function.

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